

RRING T3.3 guidelines: Responsible Research and Innovation state-of-the-art global interviews

Contact information

Any queries in preparing for the interviews, please contact monica.racovita@anglia.ac.uk

Further details on the project more generally can be found on www.rring.eu, as well as in the accompanying Participant Information Sheet.

Partners and sub-contractors selecting interview participants that do not meet the strict sampling criteria will need to provide clear and strong justifications for such deviations, in the post-interview fieldnotes survey. Should these deviations not be justifiable (with UCC having the final decision), then the partner/sub-contractor may be asked to do more interviews to make up this shortfall and/or face budgetary implications.

Please contact Monica Racovita and Chris Foulds (ARU), with Jasmin Schomakers (UCC) in cc, should you have any queries about the sampling criteria or if you would like prior approval in making unavoidable deviations from the guidelines. Contact via MSTeams is strongly preferable, although email is possible if that is easier (monica.racovita@anglia.ac.uk; chris.foulds@anglia.ac.uk; jasmin.schomakers@ucc.ie).

Document purpose and overview

This document contains detailed guidelines for preparing, conducting and reporting interviews, as part of Task 3.3 (T3.3), in Work Package 3, in the EU Horizon 2020 project: Responsible Research and Innovation Networking Globally (RRING). The interviews will be undertaken by RRING partners and additional sub-contractors.

Each interview will be approximately 60 minutes long and be in the local language. RRING partners and sub-contractors will need to invite interview participants using clearly specified selection criteria.

This document gives detailed guidance on: the selection process for the participants; reporting requirements and associated deadlines; what to do in the interviews themselves (including specific interview questions that everyone must use in the same way); and advice on interview planning and preparation. To ensure a consistent approach, as well as to aid partners and sub-contractors in this task, we have also provided consent forms, participant information sheets, contact email templates, example of transcripts, etc.

Whilst the primary purpose of this document is to provide the resources and instructions for all interviewers, we also provide some background context concerning the Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) literature (Annex 1) – note that this is only provided for those interviewer unfamiliar with RRI. Please remember it is not actually expected that RRI will explicitly feature in the interview conversation; instead, research/innovation will be discussed in more general terms, without any pre-determined labels (e.g. regarding “responsibility”).

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1 Accounting for interviewer-participant power dynamics

This section reminds the interviewer of the possible interplay between interviewers and participants, and how power plays an important role in shaping what data is included.

Power is a central aspect to consider by a successful interviewer-participant relationship. The balances of power may change when the interviewer partners with research participants as part of the community rather than entering as experts. The power dynamics become more important when there are cultural and gender differences between the parties requiring a culturally sensitive approach. There are several ways of establishing a culturally sensitive approach within the interview. The interviewer should establish a good rapport with the participant to break the ice, before embarking on the interview proper, thereby encouraging the participant to trust and share accurate information on the topic to be discussed. Without rapport, even the best-phrased questions can fall flat and elicit brief, uninformative answers. Rapport means more than just putting people at ease. It means convincing people that you are listening, that you understand and are interested in what they are talking about, and that they should continue talking.

In addition, our approach to informed consent must ensure that research participants are informed about the research and that their formal consent to participate is obtained in line with relevant cultural sensitivities.

2 Expectations of interviewers

This section summarizes the main expectations for interviewers to account for:

- You will need to select participants according to the selection criteria specified in this document (Section 2);
- You will need to conduct the number of interviews that has been allocated to you according to the criteria specified in this document (please see Annex 9 of this document);
- All reporting needs to be provided in English using the forms in this document. You will be expected to provide the audio recording and initial (pre-translation) transcript in the language in which the interview is conducted.

3 Selection of interview participants

This section details how participants will be selected, following key selection considerations, including: number of interviews; domains; stakeholder types; relevance of their professional work to the RRING project's RRI interests; gender. These are now discussed in turn in sub-sections 3.1-3.5.

After completing all the interviews and upon final reporting to ARU (i.e. final transcripts submitted), a statement must also be provided on how you met these selection criteria across all your interviews, and where/why deviations were occurred. Please do also monitor your ongoing performance against these selection criteria, as you will be receiving personal interviewer data (e.g. on genders, stakeholder types, domains, countries of work), rather than having to rely on your own assumptions.

3.1 Number of interviews

There is an absolute minimum of five interviews per country, but (given different budgets/resources available) the expectations for the total aggregate number of interviews ‘per partner/sub-contractor’ (across all countries in their remit) vary. Please ensure you are aware of the expected minimum sample for your situation (see Annex 9).

3.2 Gender of interview participants

Aim for 50% male, 50% female or other gender identities gender split between your participants. If you cannot meet this target, then a minimum of 40% female or other gender identities representation is acceptable. Regardless of difficulties, you must do everything you can to ensure there is at least one male and one female respondent in your sample.

3.3 Domains – coverage across interview participants

Ensure you have at least one of each domain category in your sample (ICT/digital; energy; waste; bio-economy). Beyond this minimum, you can sample further from particular key domains or include participants that work across multiple domains (e.g. funders of research/innovation that span all domains):

1. **Bioeconomy:** “The International Advisory Committee on Bioeconomy, set up at the occasion of the First Global Bioeconomy Summit in Berlin in November 2015, defines bioeconomy as “knowledge-based production and utilization of biological resources, biological processes and principles to sustainably provide goods and services across all economic sectors”. Bioeconomy involves three elements:
 - Renewable biomass: This concerns the use of renewable biomass and efficient bioprocesses to achieve a sustainable production;
 - Enabling and converging technologies (‘Nano-Bio-Info-Cogno’): Beyond biotechnology, a key development is the combination of digitalization and ‘biologization’. Sustainable development is supported by applications such as precision agriculture, satellite forestry monitoring, DNA barcoding of fish species, etc. In the IT industry, biological knowledge is applied to computer and chip design, e.g. DNA storage;
 - Integration across applications: Integration concerns primary production (i.e. all living natural resources), health (i.e. pharmaceuticals and medical devices), and industry (i.e. chemicals, plastics, enzymes, pulp and paper, bioenergy).” (FAO, 2016)¹

A few further examples could include: research/innovations that relate directly to the manipulation of genes, including gene editing (DNA is inserted, deleted, modified or replaced in the genome of a living organism), as well as the manipulation of RNA and proteins, synbiotech (fabrication of biological components and systems that do not already exist in the natural world), nanobiotech (nanomaterials, nanoelectronics, nanometrology, molecular self-assemblies, nanorobotics, etc.), and bioinformatics (biological studies that use computer programming as part of their methodology).

¹ Food and Agriculture Organization (2016). How sustainability is addressed in official bioeconomy strategies at international, national and regional levels: An overview. Rome: FAO. <http://www.fao.org/3/a-i5998e.pdf>

2. **Waste management:** “waste prevention, reuse/recycling, treatment and disposal” (UNEP)². In practice they can be research/innovations that relate to some part or all of the waste systems (i.e. across the lifecycle of a product/service, from manufacturing, through use and maintenance, to disposal). They can also be research/innovations that are enabling us to get more out of resources that would otherwise be disposed of or even unnecessarily recycled (too early, when e.g. re-use is still possible)? Such waste management streams could be wide-ranging, including e.g. food, plastics, water, medicines.
3. **Energy:** “The energy system comprises all components related to the production, conversion, delivery, and use of energy.”³ Research/innovations that related to some part or all of energy system, from how energy is supplied (e.g. micro-generation schemes; shifting to low-carbon sources) or distributed (e.g. micro-grids; smart grids; integration across grids), to how energy is consumed by citizens and businesses (e.g. heating; mobility; lighting).
4. **Information & Communications Technologies (ICT):** “covers all technical means used to handle information and aid communication. This includes both computer and network hardware, as well as their software” (EU)⁴. That would include all technologies that enable the collection and handling of information to facilitate different forms of communication and use for societal benefit; research/innovations that focus on enhanced connectivity for societies (e.g. access to internet and/or broadband speeds), as well as advancements that are possible through e.g. artificial intelligence or the internet of things.

3.4 Stakeholder types of interview participants

The stakeholder types are as follows:

- *Research organisation:* entity such as institute, centre or university, regardless of whether it is public or private, whose main goal is to conduct basic or applied research
- *Research funding organisation:* entities, either public (e.g. governmental organizations) or private (e.g. charities) who are major funders of research projects
- *Industry and business:* entity involved in a commercial or industrial enterprise
- *Civil society organisation:* entities separated either from the State or the market; they exclude industry or any for-profit organizations; have a declared social mandate
- *Policy bodies:* public entities that explore issues and concerns of public interest and develop policies and recommendations

When approaching prospective interview participants, please consider their stakeholder type on the basis of how their own organisation publicly classified/labels itself (e.g. in its “About us” webpage descriptions, or its “Corporate mission statement”, etc.). Do also note that we require evidence of your thinking of this – specifically through screenshots and weblinks of such webpages. When reporting please upload the screenshot with the background of the respondent (Details in Section 11 of this document, Reporting). You are expected to monitor this criterion for each interview

² UNEP, Chemicals and waste management, <https://www.undp.org/content/undp/en/home/sustainable-development/environment-and-natural-capital/chemicals-and-waste-management.html>

³ https://www.ipcc.ch/site/assets/uploads/2018/02/ipcc_wg3_ar5_annex-i.pdf

⁴ EUROSTAT [https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Glossary:Information_and_communication_technology_\(ICT\)](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Glossary:Information_and_communication_technology_(ICT))

participant post-interview, as you will have received the signed Consent Form, which includes a question on stakeholder types.

Ensure you have at least one of each stakeholder type, if your organisation is conducting more than 5 interviews (care must be taken to ensure that the stakeholder base is drawn from a diverse pool). If you are doing less than 5 or exactly 5, please have at least 3 categories of stakeholders represented in your interviewing pool. Remember that some stakeholders can belong to multiple categories, thus multiple stakeholder categories can be ticked for a single interview participant.

3.5 Nationality and country of residence

We are interested in research and innovation experiences in the selected countries. However, due to the global nature of research and innovation and the increased mobility of professionals in these fields, potential interview participants with in-depth knowledge of particular country contexts might not be citizens or even residents of those countries at the time of the interview. Such participants can and should be selected, provided that their expertise and knowledge in the country context you are conducting your interviews on can be proven. Please be sure to provide a particularly clear explanation for the choice of selecting a participant (in the online field notes, question 12, please see Annex 4 for details) when they are not citizens and/or are not current residents of the country in which you are conducting interviews.

3.6 RRI-like focus of interview participants' work

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) is a European term. Even within Europe, there is considerable disagreement over the possible interpretations of the term. Thus, we should assume participants will not be familiar with the term and associated practices. However, without using the RRI terminology, their approaches to research and innovation might display RRI-like characteristics (e.g. efforts to enhance gender equality, a collaboration with a wide array of stakeholders in development of research and innovation, concerns and plans for future social impacts of a technology). The most revealing interviews may come from individuals involved in work that includes such characteristics. A short online search into the background of the participants, prior to selection, could indicate the presence of any publicly visible RRI-like activities undertaken by the respondents. It is vital you do this before inviting anyone to interview, to ensure that their work complements the innovation/research approaches that RRING would find useful to investigate.

The RRI frame we employ in this task includes, but is not limited to, elements of the process dimensions of RRI (see image below), RRI pillars⁵, AIRR dimensions⁶ and SDGs⁷. However, the selected participants do not need to meet all or any of these characteristics for selection (Process dimensions, pillars, AIRR dimensions, or SDGs). In relation to the EU pillars: "RRING incorporates ...these keys. However, RRING recognises that they do not factor in geographic diversity including culture, governance and Grand Challenges=" (RRING grant agreement, p. 28).

⁵ EU RRI pillars: Ethics, Gender equality, Open access and data, Science education, Public engagement, Governance <http://www.rring.eu/>

⁶ AIRR dimensions: Anticipation, Inclusion, Reflexion, Responsiveness
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0048733313000930>

⁷ SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals)
<https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/sustainable-development-goals/>.

Process dimensions

To reach these outcomes, practicing a more responsible research and innovation requires that processes are:

Diverse & inclusive: involve early a wide range of actors and publics in R&I practice, deliberation, and decision-making to yield more useful and higher quality knowledge. This strengthens democracy and broadens sources of expertise, disciplines and perspectives.

Anticipative & reflective: envision impacts and reflect on the underlying assumptions, values, and purposes to better understand how R&I shapes the future. This yields to valuable insights and increase our capacity to act on what we know.

Open & transparent: communicate in a balanced, meaningful way methods, results, conclusions, and implications to enable public scrutiny and dialogue. This benefits the visibility and understanding of R&I.

Responsive & adaptive to change: be able to modify modes of thought and behaviour, overarching organizational structures, in response to changing circumstances, knowledge, and perspectives. This aligns action with the needs expressed by stakeholders and publics.

Process dimensions of RRI: From the RRI Tools website (www.rri-tools.eu/about-rri)

4 Getting informed consent from interview participants

This section details actions and scenarios that should be taken to obtain consent from the participants.

Potential participants should be contacted using the email template provided (Annex 2). The Participant Information Sheet and Consent Form (Annex 3) should be attached to this email. If interest to participate is given, a date and time will be set according to the availability of the participant and of the interviewer (giving priority to the participant).

In the template email, we explain that the Consent Form “would need to be signed and returned to [X3] before conducting the interviews”. Given the professional environments that many of the interview participants will be working in, they may well return the consent form signed, and with no issues. However, should there be queries with this process (e.g. what is considered acceptable), please see the following 5 scenarios for how you can obtain informed consent from your interview participants:

No.	Ask the respondent by email: <i>“Do you prefer to send the signed Consent Form with...”</i>	Instructions
1.	<i>“...a digital signature?”</i>	If the participant has a digital signature and access to email, the participant can email a digital version of the Consent Form to the interviewer.
2.	<i>“...by phone camera?”</i>	Participants can print, sign, take a photo using their phone, and send by email to the interviewer.
3.	<i>“...scanned and sent by email?”</i>	Participant has access to email, printer and scanner, and thus can email a scanned signed Consent Form to the interviewer.
4.	<i>“...bring it in person?”</i>	The interview is face-to-face and the Consent Form is signed in paper form. In this case, the interviewer must ensure there

		will be two signed copies: one for the interviewer and one for the participant.
5.	"...none of the above?"	If the participant cannot return the Consent Form through options 1-3 and is not doing the interview face-to-face (option 5), then the interviewer must read the Consent Form (without the section for engaging in further RRING activities) at the very beginning of the interview. An audio recording of this reading and of the interview participant subsequent verbal consent must be obtained.

Please remember that it can take time for participants to read, sign and return the Consent Form. We suggest the following steps and timescales:

- *When inviting the participant to be interviewed:* send Consent Form and Participant Information Sheet, as per the email template (Annex 2). Do not send an invitation email with less than a week before possible interview times/dates, as you will likely find it difficult to receive (and/or chase for responses on) the signed Consent Form.
- *Request that the Consent Form be signed and returned in 1-week:* should the Consent Form not be signed by your 1-week deadline, do contact them to politely chase and ask if there are any issues you can clarify. Obviously, you should not wait a whole week, if you only sent the forms to the prospective participant one week before the agreed interview date. Ultimately, please show sensitively as we should not appear rude, but getting these signed Consent Forms back is absolutely essential.
- *If no response on the Consent Form or you face concerns:* Email the participant to offer the various options, as set out in the above table. It is fine to e.g. follow option 5 (in the table) to get audio recorded consent if absolutely necessary, but this MUST be pre-agreed (in theory) over email beforehand. Otherwise, you may risk wasting both interviewer and participant time, if it turns out there is real apprehension about giving consent that was not suitably addressed pre-interview. Therefore – if there is no response on the consent form – you will have no choice but to politely delay the interview date.

The interview must not proceed in the absence of the signed Consent Form, or in the absence of an audio recording of the participant agreeing to the exact contents of the Consent Form (option 5 in the table above – but this is not the preferred option).

5 Audio recording the interview

The expectation is that every interview will be audio recorded, with the recordings (.mp3) submitted alongside the transcripts as part of the reporting to ARU. Please be sure to save this recording to your computer (or the MS Teams folder) as soon as possible – ideally immediately afterwards – to avoid the situation where the recording is damaged/lost (if incomplete materials are handed over, the interview may not be usable and associated person-months may not be approved).

For interviews conducted over Skype or phone we recommend the use of Amolto Recorder, a free software that can connect with Skype and record any call done through a particular Skype account towards either another Skype account or phone.

If the participant refuses to be recorded, please ensure another person is present during the interview whose sole role is to take very detailed notes, which are as close to verbatim as possible (with exact quotations noted on critical issues). To reiterate: this additional interviewer will not be asking any questions. In this eventuality, please ensure that your handwritten notes are more fully typed up into an MS Word document as soon as possible after the interview (ideally immediately).

Face-to-face interviews must be conducted in areas free from distractions/noises, to help ensure high quality audio recordings.

Do also ensure that your audio recording device (whether it is your mobile phone or a dictaphone) has been well-tested, has enough battery, and has enough memory space (consider using a second ‘back-up recorder as well).

6 Instructions at the start of the interview, before asking any interview questions

This section details interviewer actions needed **before** starting to ask the interview questions.

What to say to ALL interview participants	Accompanying guidance
“Were there any problems with the Participant Information Sheet and Consent Form? Do you have copies of each?”	Have signed duplicates for your own records, if conducting the interview face-to-face
“I need to remind you that the interview will be recorded. I can reassure you that anything you say will be anonymized before being shared publicly.”	
“I would like to remind you that that you have been invited because we want to get your perspective on research and innovation. Your work has a direct connection to the key domains we are investigating (<i>digital/ICT; energy; bio-economy; waste management</i>).”	<i>Select the domain(s) that match [skip this statement for ‘cross-domain’ participants]</i>
“Can we continue with the interview?”	If ‘yes’, turn audio recorder on.

After going through the above questions and statements, you can turn your audio recorder(s) ON and start your interview questions (Annex 5).

7 Advice for during the interview, whilst asking the interview questions

This section draws attention to the behaviour of the interviewer during the interview.

- Neutral, polite, encouraging tone should be employed throughout the interview

- Where you have the option of choosing between multiple interviewers from your particular partner/sub-contractor to do the interview, it is important to remember the role of gender dynamics. Therefore, if possible, female participants should be interviewed by a female interviewers. If that is not possible, then the male interviewer should be aware of gender power dynamics and wherever possible should create a space where the interview participant feels comfortable. Specifically, the interviewer should be sure to use gender sensitive language (e.g. in discussions, do not say “he” or “she” when the gender role is unknown use “they”) and give equal value to both women’s and men’s experiences (e.g. when probing more deeply into professional experiences of colleagues and others in the interview participant’s networks).
- Other diversity dynamics: it may not always be possible to match participants and interviewers on grounds of their personal characteristics but care must be taken to promote dignity, respect, inclusivity and cultural awareness at all times during the interview. For example language use must be appropriate.
- Body language (in face-to-face interviews) of the interviewer should be carefully composed in order to avoid giving participants the impression that certain answers would be more positively received than others.

8 Instructions for the end of the interview, after asking all the interview questions

This section details the actions of the interviewer at the end of the interview.

Instruction on WHEN to note each respective issue	WHAT interviewer should say to participant regarding each respective issue
<p>If the participant expressed concerns about his/her anonymity at the start of the interview, then please reiterate how we will address this point.</p>	<p>“I would also like to remind you that all your answers will be anonymized before any quotes[, translated into English,] will be made public.”</p> <p><i>[obviously please exclude the “translated into English”, if you are doing the interview in English]</i></p>
<p><u>For all interview participants</u>, be sure to finish by emphasising that you are grateful for their time and are available post-interview for any queries they may have.</p>	<p>“Thank you; I really appreciate you kindly giving your time to answer my questions. You have my contact details, and so please do not hesitate to contact me if you have any questions or concerns.”</p> <p><i>[if your interview was not arranged by you, and thus they do not have your e.g. individual email address, then please change the final sentence above and give them your details. It is important that they can follow-up with you, if needed.]</i></p>

9 Instructions for post-interview reporting

This section details the actions for after the interview.

- Transcribe the interview in the language it was conducted in. Then, translate the transcript into English if it was originally conducted in a non-English language. After this process is complete, undertake a simple anonymization process to remove the name of the participant, as well as names of places, companies, etc.; replace these with codes. E.g. Instead of Mr Sam Smith, the name of the participant, write Mr Br1 (Br stands for country⁸, if Brazil in this example, and 1 for the first interview you conduct in that country). Each of these steps must be saved in a separate file, clearly labelled.
- After the interview has ended, write down your impressions (field notes). Please use the online form developed for this purpose (Annex 3). We recommend writing your field notes immediately after your interview (e.g. ideally within 1 hour of finishing), although you are able to refine and edit your notes up to the deadline of submitting the field notes within one week post-interview. It is also good practice to keep short, concise (perhaps keywords-based) notes during the interview itself, which can then act as a useful prompt when coming back later to write the fuller version of your field notes.
- **Within two weeks of the interview (for final deadline please contact the task leader):**
 - Transcript in local language (unless local language was English, then not required)
 - Transcript in English: 2 versions = 1 anonymized and 1 non-anonymized.
 - Field notes in English, using the online field notes form
 - Audio recording of the interview
 - The signed Consent Form
 - Screenshots with information on respondents' background demonstrating their suitability for being selected for interview
 - Copy of follow-up email sent to interview participant, with a copy of the local language transcript, which gives them the option to say they are unhappy with the contents.

Please note that all of these steps must be completed in order for you to have been considered to have completed an interview.

10 Transcription guidance

This section details the transcription process. Please write down everything that was said during the interview, word by word. Please see an example of a first page of a transcript in Annex 6; be sure to follow this template when producing your transcript, as it is vital that all transcripts are constructed in the same way.

We expect 100% accuracy in the transcriptions; there can be no transcription errors⁹. ARU will conduct random quality checks that compare the audio recordings and the transcripts.

Transcription is a meticulous and time-consuming enterprise, so remember:

- **Time for transcription:** For the manual, unassisted transcription, an estimate of about 6 hours of transcription per hour of audio recording is expected.

⁸ Please use the International Vehicle Registration Code system to identify the relevant code for each country/interview: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/International_vehicle_registration_code.

⁹ Transcription errors will indicate that the interview task was not fully completed.

- **Differentiate speakers in transcript:** Capture the speech of both the interviewer and participant, and ensure that ‘interviewer text’ is written in a different colour (interviewer=blue; participant=black).
- **No need to transcribe non-word communications:** As we will not be conducting discourse analysis, we will not need to transcribe e.g. pauses, coughs, ‘umms’ and ‘errs’, laughs, etc.
- **Record time stamps at the point you start a new interview question in the transcripts:** Only time stamp at the point you are starting a new question in the interview (i.e. we do not need to record the exact time at which certain words/phrases were spoken).
- **You can choose to use software to aid your transcription:** You can either manually transcribe the audio recording or you can use software that helps you speed up the process, by giving you better control over forward and backward functions for example. Either way, you will have to thoroughly go through the text to ensure it accurately details the interview discussion word for word.
- **You can use automated transcript software:** You can use fully automated transcription services (like Scribie, for example). Please note that you might need to pay for transcription in this case. Additional funding for these services will not be provided. Please also note that often such automated transcription software is only available for English. Different accents are often not well recognized by the software giving accuracies of around 80%. A manual check will need to be employed to bring accuracy to 100%.
- **Check meaning:** Go back to the participant and check that the transcript reflects what they meant to say (see Annex 7 for an email template). Give a deadline (1 week) by when they need to reply. Mention that if we do not hear from them by the mentioned deadline, we will assume that all is fine.
- **Provide an additional anonymized version of each transcript:** After completing your local language transcription of your interview, and after then generating your second translated (into English) transcript, please do a simple anonymization of the English transcript: e.g. remove names of people, places and institutions that could help identify the participant and replace them with code (e.g. “we went to London to investigate” “we went to B to investigate”).
- **Ensure you have three transcripts to submit per interview if language is other than English:** Please submit both an anonymized transcript (in English) and two non-anonymized transcripts (one in local language – obviously only required if local language is not English; and one translated into English).

11 Reporting requirements

This section details the actions to be undertaken for reporting purposes. These materials must be submitted as soon as they are ready. For instance, **DO NOT WAIT TO COMPLETE ALL OF THE INTERVIEWS BEFORE SUBMITTING** the outputs from each interview.

11.1 To be submitted via MS Teams after each interview

The partners/sub-contractors should **submit the following from each interview via MS Teams:**

1. Audio recording of the interview
2. Signed and dated Consent Form
3. The transcription in the original language

4. 2 (English) translated versions of each transcripts
 - a. anonymized
 - b. non-anonymized (to be shared among RRING partners)
5. Copy of email sent to interview participant, with a copy of the local language transcript, which gives them the option to say they are unhappy with the contents.
6. Screenshots with information on respondents' background demonstrating their suitability for being interviewed

Partners must submit these files in MS Teams via the following route:

WP3 > T3.3 > Interviews reporting_Active > [partner folder name]> [Interview participant code] (Please set up new subfolders for each participant when reporting)

Sub-contractors must submit these files in MS Teams, and can do so via their own dedicated MS Teams folder, named after their countries, which have been setup with ARU, UCC and HSRW.

11.2 To be submitted via the online form after each interview

The partners/sub-contractors should **submit from each interview via the online form**:

Completed online field notes form (in English). Please **complete this field notes form within 1 week of the interview**. We also strongly advise the majority of these notes should be written up immediately after the interview itself.

It is exactly the same process for submission, regardless of whether you are a partner or sub-contractor. All answers to be submitted via:

<https://angliaruskin.onlinesurveys.ac.uk/rring-field-notes> (more details on the questions included in this survey, in Annex 4).

11.3 To be submitted via MS Teams once all the interviews (and interview-specific reporting) are finished

The partners/subcontractor should also submit the following via MS Teams, after they have finished all of the interviews and completed all the interview-specific reporting:

1. Names and contact information of the interview participants willing to be in WP5 interviews
2. Statement of performance against interview participant selection criteria, with justifications if targets not met across your sample

The folder location for uploading to MS Teams is the same, as instructed in sub-section 11.1.

11.4 Reporting deadlines

We ask for:

- Immediate uploading of the audio recording files and signed Consent Forms.
- Completion of the online fieldnotes form within one week of an interview.
- Submission of the transcripts within two weeks of an interview.

Please check with Monica Racovita (monica.racovita@anglia.ac.uk) for the final deadline for all reporting.

12 ANNEX 1: Background literature on global Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) debates [context purposes only, for those new to RRI]

The purpose of this section is to familiarize the reader with Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) and the most important developments associated with it. In particular, we looked for any attempts to define a global approach for RRI.

A scoping of the literature, both of projects and of academic research, showed that there are very few attempts for a global RRI and many, when undertaken, are devised for particular stakeholders (e.g. industry) or domains (e.g. health).

An earlier EU-funded project, PROGRESS, took as a point of reference the Lund Declaration which emphasized the need for innovation to meet grand societal challenges. The project recognized that these challenges can be different depending on context. Indeed the project found that outside of the EU context and Western values, the societal challenges can sharply differ. Yet, although the findings indicated that there is no convergence in terms of tackling the same challenges, a common interest was uncovered by the project in tailoring innovation policies to addressing context-bound grand challenges (Engelhard, et al., 2015). The project indicated as a possible proxy for RRI societal desirability while acknowledging that this can mean different things for different people (Cavallaro, et al., 2014).

The connection between RRI and societal challenges at the global scale was also pursued in academic literature (Voegtlin & Scherer, 2017). Researchers like Voegtlin and Scherer equate responsible innovation with innovation done in support of SDGs on the dimensions of 'do no harm', 'do good', and govern these two dimensions at global level through soft law.

An insightful systematic review of responsible innovation practices in the business context (Lubberink, et al., 2017) looks at the intertwining of related concepts of RRI, social innovation and sustainable innovation. It takes the AIRR dimensions (anticipation, inclusion, reflexion and responsiveness) into consideration when looking at RRI like practices. The authors recognize that the model they propose can only apply to the 'global North' (United States, Canada, Europe, Australia and New Zealand) as it is being developed based on a European definition and conceptualization of RRI, and it would not make sense being applied directly to other socio-cultural contexts.

Other researchers expressed doubts over the potential of the RRI concept to be pursued at a global level, mainly due to its Western bias. Wong (2016) indicates the need to return to the foundations of RRI and open it to other normative traditions. He envisions two major sets of challenges: theoretical, as it opens the gate towards relativism (which values to consider, where, and of whom? And which values should take priority in case of a conflict?) and practical (as little has been done in the direction of exploring other normative foundations for RRI).

Outside of the geographical scope, Schroeder and Iatridis (2016) doubt whether the concept is applicable to all stakeholders in particular for industry. They conclude that in comparison to CSI (Corporate Social Investment), RRI is both wider and narrower: wider because it asks industry to concern itself with wider societal needs and desirability (going beyond 'do no harm' to 'do good'), and narrower because instead of looking at the whole business cycle it only focuses on R&D. Schroeder and Iatridis (ibid.) do not account for cultural differences.

On a similar line, other opt for taking the argument of RRI suitability for different categories of stakeholders further by constructing RRI frameworks that are specific for particular industries: e.g.

global health innovations (Silva, et al., 2018), or ICT (focused on ethical and social impacts, societal needs and engaging stakeholders) (Porcari, et al., 2015).

Other researchers investigated whether the EU RRI keys are appropriate for a global pursuit of RRI. The EU-funded project RRI Practice conducted 12 workshops on RRI in Australia, Brazil, Bulgaria, China, France, Germany, India, Italy, the Netherlands, Norway, the United Kingdom and the United States. The report concludes that awareness for RRI as a concept is low, albeit upon introduction and further discussion the concept is received positively. Despite wide context-bound differences, RRI achieved common ground in a shared understanding that innovation should be “oriented towards societal needs, be useful to society and be mission oriented” (Owen, et al., 2017, p.1). In general, participants in these workshops viewed the EU RRI keys as somewhat constrictive to the wide transformative potential of RRI. To this end the AIRR dimensions (anticipation, inclusion, reflexion and responsiveness) were found to be better suited. Nonetheless, the EU keys were found to be commonly included in national activities related to innovation, with the exception of science education which proved to be too vague. Specific issues connected to particular political, economic and social contexts were mentioned as well. For example, in India a broader concept of equity that would go beyond gender equality was proposed. In other contexts it was suggested that stakeholder engagement would be done only superficially, without any real input into decision-making (ibid.).

As regards the language used to represent the concept, the word ‘responsibility’ proved problematic as it conveys different cultural meanings: from being equated with accountability to being completely foreign to open access (ibid.).

Participants further underlined the need to consider research separately from innovation, as they operate under different structures. For example, involving stakeholders is more readily found in industry while open access has less IPR-related restrictions in publicly funded research. They conclude that the EU RRI keys apply better to publicly-funded research (ibid.).

The presence and pursuit of EU RRI keys were also investigated in another EU-funded project, NUCLEUS. Similarly to RRI practice, NUCLEUS discovered that although addressed in policies, the EU keys are not the most important components of responsible innovation in various countries outside of Europe. Instead issues like the responsibility of researchers in China and indigenous knowledge in South Africa were prioritized (Dijkstra, et al., 2017).

Another project, COMPASS, investigated the applicability of the EU keys for the European industry concluding that the industry might have other priorities regarding responsible innovation. One deliverable (Antoniou, 2017) investigates several potential RRI aspects important for SMEs: social innovation; open innovation; environmental considerations; ethical considerations; codes of conduct; gender and workplace equality. The review further identified benefits for SMEs that promoted these RRI aspects, among which most important were: financial gains, increased productivity and decreased costs, enhanced business reputation, increased access to resources, and enhanced workforce morale (ibid.).

In another deliverable, that aimed to assess the integration of the RRI approach into collaborative R&D&I and SMEs in European funded research, authors selected as main dimensions of RRI the ones specified in the EU keys framework (gender, open access, public engagement, ethics, science education), to which they added sustainable development and corporate social responsibility (CSR) (Nwafor, et al., 2017). Among the projects reviewed, the majority seem to address RRI in a holistic way, although many still pursued only one RRI key. The most frequently investigated key (within these projects) was public engagement, while the least frequently investigated was gender.

13 ANNEX 2: Contact email template

Explanation:

X1 and X2: It is important that these fields are tailored to each prospective participant. They need to feel that this isn't a mass mail-out and that you have carefully chosen them because they really have something to offer us.

X3: person conducting the interview, in theory the person sending the email as well

X4: Give polite deadline for response to your email, as per your own work schedule. Suggest to put this date in bold.

Please remember to translate this into the language in which the interviews will be conducted.

Dear [...],

We would like to invite you for an interview on your experiences with research and innovation.

This interview would form part of the EU Horizon 2020 'Responsible Research and Innovation Networking Globally' ([RRING](#)) project. These interviews will be gathering insights into research and innovation practices – including e.g. governance and regulation frameworks, and the roles and interaction of the stakeholders – in the context of digital (ICT), energy, bio-economy, and/or waste management fields. This contributes to the development of global networks of R&I.

The key reason for why we have approached you is because of your significant expertise in [X1]. We are keen to hear about your experiences in initiatives such as [X2]. Ultimately, we are really eager to learn from your insights concerning how research and innovation are being pursued in your country and respective field.

By participating in this interview, you will be contributing to the formation of an international approach to research and innovation, which reflects the realities of your context (geographic, social, economic, etc.). You will also be in the unique position where your ideas will be directly feeding into the setup of a new global network on RRI, hosted by UNESCO. We can happily provide you with the outputs from this research task too, so that you can get a sense of what other established researchers/innovators feel about some of the same 'big issues'.

It is important to note though: you are under no obligation to take part in the research and declining to take part will have no influence on future engagements with any of the partners in the RRING project or indeed with any participants of the future UNESCO-hosted network. Participation is entirely voluntary, and we have received ethical approval to carry out this research.

However, should this opportunity interest you, then the interview would take approximately 45-60 minutes. It will be audio recorded and/or notes will be taken during it. Further information on the interview itself is available in the attached Participant Information Sheet. In addition, please find attached a Consent Form, which would need to be signed and returned to [X3] before conducting the interviews.

The interview would be conducted over telephone or skype or in person; we can accommodate whatever your preference is. As I am sure you can imagine, we are in the midst of arranging multiple interviews in parallel, and thus we would be very grateful if you could respond to our invitation by [X4]. An indication of possible dates/times for the interview would also be very useful.

If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to ask.

Looking forward to hearing from you.

Sincerely,

[interviewer details]

Participant Information Sheet

1. Why are we doing this study?

This study is part of the EU-funded ‘Responsible Research and Innovation Networking Globally’ (RRING) project, which seeks to explore how good research practices are established in different research and innovation contexts across the world.

The study, in which we invite you to take part, aims to get insights into: key policies and drivers; governance and regulation frameworks; key platforms spaces, networks and players; and roles and interactions of the key stakeholders. We are also specifically interested in professionals working in the **digital (ICT), energy, bio-economy and waste management** fields.

2. Who are we?

The Global Sustainability Institute at Anglia Ruskin University, Cambridge, UK, is coordinating this study within RRING. This is in collaboration with partners and subcontractors from several countries including, among others, EU member states, US, South Africa, India and Japan.

3. Why are we asking you to take part?

You have been invited because we want to hear your perspective on research and innovation. Your work has a direct connection to at least one of the key domains we are investigating (digital/ICT; energy; bio-economy; waste management), and thus you are in the position to provide valuable insights into the way research and innovation are being pursued in your country and relevant domain. By participating in this survey, you will be contributing to the formation of an international approach on research and innovation, which reflects the realities of your context (geographic, social, economic, etc.). You are under no obligation to take part in the research and declining to take part will have no influence on future engagements with any of the partners in the RRING project.

4. What does being interviewed involve?

Participation is entirely voluntary. We will invite you to take part in an approximately 60 minute interview pursuing in more detail the research and innovation issues investigated in a previous global survey. More specifically, the interview will involve an informal conversation on the context in which the respondent conducts research/innovation and it will involve policies and drivers, governance and regulation frameworks, key

platforms, spaces, networks and players, roles and interactions of stakeholders. The interviews **will be audio recorded** and/or notes taken during it.

5. How will your data be used?

The results of these interviews will feed into several RRING deliverables and at least one peer-reviewed academic paper, all of which will be made freely available online. We would like to assure you that when presenting the results of these interviews outside of the project, quotes translated in English might be shown, but we will ensure that the resulting data cannot be attributed to a specific respondent (unless you specifically express a desire to promote your project/company/institution).

You have the option to withdraw before the interview commences (even if you have agreed to participate) or to discontinue participation after data collection has started. You may do so within two weeks of participation and ask to have your data destroyed. If you wish to do so, please contact (**email address of the interviewer**).

Data will be held securely by the core research team at Anglia Ruskin University and will only be fully shared with other researchers in the RRING project (and anonymized before it is shared outside of the RRING project). All survey data will be treated according to the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Your personal information is available only to RRING researchers. On completion of the project, the full dataset will be retained at ARU for maximum two years following the completion of the project (i.e. until 30 April 2023) and then destroyed. Anonymised data will be published in accordance with European Commission open data policies.

6. How to contact us?

If you have any questions regarding this study please contact monica.racovita@anglia.ac.uk. If you have inquiries regarding the overall project, please contact rring.eu@gmail.com. For further information on the project, you can find details on www.rring.eu.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 788503.

RRING state-of-the-art global interviews on research & innovation activities

CONSENT FORM

- I am 18 years old or over.
- I agree to take part in the interview. I have read the information sheet and I understand what my role will be. I understand I am free to ask further questions at any time.
- I understand that I am free to withdraw my data within two weeks of the interview, without giving a reason, by contacting the interviewer.
- I understand what will happen to the data collected from me for the research.
- I have been provided with a copy of this information sheet and consent form.
- I understand the interview will be recorded and that anonymised quotes may be used in RRING materials.
- I agree to the RRING consortium processing personal data that I have supplied. I agree to the processing of such data for any purposes connected with RRING, as outlined to me. I understand my data may be shared with RRING partners, some of whom are based outside the EU, but all of whom are contractually bound to abide by EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) law. I understand personal data will be held for a maximum of 2 years post-project (i.e. up to 30 April 2023), after which time it will be destroyed.

Please also confirm with your interviewer whether (only one option needs to be ticked to proceed, and you can change your option within two weeks):

- you are happy to be named in the general acknowledgements of the state-of-the art RRING report(s) (not associated with individual responses and quotes); or,
- you would rather remain completely confidential, with your company name not mentioned anywhere.

ONLY FOR INDUSTRY PARTICIPANTS: In addition, as part of the same study, our colleagues within RRING would like to ask you a few questions about competitive advantage and its link to innovation:

- I agree to be contacted for an additional interview focused on responsible research and innovation and its link to competitive advantage.

Please fill in:

1. The country you are officially based in for work is
2. Which other countries, if any, does your work also regularly focus on.....
.....?
3. Your nationality is
4. Your organization could be classified as being a (please select, one or more)
 - Research organization
 - Research funder
 - Industry
 - Civil society organization
 - Policymaking body
5. The domain(s) that your work fits within is (are) (please select, one or more)
 - Energy
 - Waste
 - Bio-economy
 - ICT/digital
6. Your job title in your organization is
7. Your gender (please select)
 - male;
 - female;
 - other;
 - rather not say.

Signed by participant: _____

Date: _____

Signed by interviewer: _____

Date: _____

Interview reference no. (to be completed by interviewer): _____

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 788503

15 ANNEX 4: Field notes due from each interview

Please fill in the following online form: <https://angliaruskin.onlinesurveys.ac.uk/rring-field-notes>

The main questions you will need to reply to, include:

- Justify the selection of the participants
- Did the participant struggle to make sense of any of the interview questions? (if so, did you need to provide additional information / clarification – if so, what did you say exactly?)
- What was the degree of familiarity with RRI or RRI-like dimensions?
- How concerned was the interviewee about anonymity?
- How comfortable/uncomfortable was the atmosphere for discussion?
- Were there any gender or cultural related observations that facilitated/hampered the interview?
- Any specific moments where you feel, as the interviewer, you influenced the interviewee? e.g. questions you asked, setup of the interview, framing of the whole study, interactions and responses during your discussion.
- Reflections on the structured nature of the interview?
- Any reflections or recommendations for how you would now seek to improve future interviews, based upon this interview experience?

16 ANNEX 5: Interview questions

16.1 Context for the interviewers

The research objective for these structured qualitative interviews is to gain a ‘bottom-up’ perspective on RRI that reveals the local practices and policies that are employed to establish research and innovation that is aligned to societal needs and values.

This objective requires a focus on perspectives, processes and practices that are employed around the world to ensure that research and innovation is ethical, socially inclusive and addressing public concerns.

16.2 Principles for interviewers

1. Conduct the interviews in the language that your participant is most comfortable with; clarify the chosen language before you send the Participant Information Sheet and Consent Form.
2. Structured interviews rely on a fixed list of questions that all participants are asked in the same order and phrasing. Certain follow-up questions for clarification purposes (specified in the table below) are allowed, but you should not pursue new domains or topics beyond what is included in the interview questions.
3. You are also allowed to ask additional clarifying/follow-up probes (e.g. “tell me more about x”; “what did you mean by x?”; etc.), but again these must remain focused on the lines of discussions already underway – please use the guidance in the second and third columns to guide you here, as appropriate.

Any queries in preparing for the interviews, please send your clarification query to monica.racovita@anglia.ac.uk, documenting any requested adjustments to the protocol that you feel are needed and why for review and approval. Please send requests as early as possible in the process, allowing a minimum of three full working days for a response.

Further details on the project more generally can be found on www.rring.eu, as well as in the accompanying Participant Information Sheet.

Interview questions:

- 7 days prior to starting the interview, check that the consent form has been completed in full. If it has not been, send a reminder.
- If the day before the interview, the consent form has still not been completed, either reschedule the interview or prepare to administer the pre-interview survey verbally before starting the interview (this would be recorded in a separate audio file because it does not need to be transcribed and translated, and it does not count towards the interview duration).
- Before starting, please confirm with the interview participant:
 - “Were there any problems with the Participant Information Sheet and Consent Form?”
 - If yes, please seek detail. If the issues relate to the consent form, please re-confirm consent verbally (using the exact wording from the consent form itself – i.e. please read each point of consent exactly as it is written) on a separate recording before starting the main interview recording

#	Interview questions to ask	Interviewer guidance, including clarifying questions and follow-up prompts	Rationale for line of questioning
1	What types of activities are you involved in that relate to research or innovation?	Select the term ‘research’ or ‘innovation’ based on what will be most relevant to the participant. That is, depending on whether the participant is clearly an academic researcher (use term ‘research’), or clearly working in e.g. technical innovation (use term ‘innovation’). If you are <u>unsure</u> which would be most relevant to the participant, use the inclusive term ‘research or innovation’.	The aim is for RRING to learn about scope of the activities the respondents are involved in to clarify the context for subsequent responses. This acts as an easy ‘warm-up question’ for interview participants, i.e. focuses on their day-to-day experiences that the participant will be comfortable talking about. Also gives useful context for all the other questions.
Public engagement			
2	In engaging the public, how does your work involve individuals or organisations from outside of your team and your type of institution? <i>[NOTE: Depending on the answer, this question funnels participant questions down 2a) or 2b) paths below]</i>	If the participant only talks about internal colleagues or about their own relatively isolated work, then ask: “Can I then confirm that you do NOT work with individuals or organisations outside your area of activity?” (e.g. if you are interviewing an academic, you would be asking about people from outside academia).	The aim is for the project to learn about public engagement and professional collaborations in their research and innovation work, which may or may not be aligned with specific ‘projects’.
2a	<i>If the participant is positive in their response to Q2, ask:</i> i. What <u>types</u> of outside individuals or organisations, have you involved in your work? ii. How do you <u>include</u> people or organizations from outside of your	<i>For all 2a) questions, ONLY ask them if they have not already been covered in the open response to Q2).</i> i. If the participant continues to talk in generic terms, or does not talk about classifications of collaborators or stakeholders (e.g. fields/disciplines/sectors/topics/etc.), then provide them with some further context: “The project aims to learn about types of players involved in enacting the public engagement	

	<p>group in your work? (What role do they have?)</p> <p><i>At this point please say to the participant: "In each section of this interview I will ask you about rules, regulations and practices, either formal ones at governmental and institutional level, or informal ones, embodied by norms and practices of your field."</i></p> <p>iii. In your professional experience, what <u>government</u> policies and regulations affect the process of involving outside groups?</p> <p>iv. What <u>institutional</u> policies or regulations within <u>your</u> current or former organisation affect the process of involving outside groups?</p> <p>v. What <u>norms and practices</u> in your field affect the process of involving outside groups?</p>	<p>dimension of research or innovation. What groups of players have you worked with?"</p> <p>ii. If the participant does not talk about the process (e.g. mechanisms guiding stakeholder interactions; timings; roles; purposes), then rephrase the question: "At what points in the process of developing your work are outside people or organisations included, and how is this addressed?"</p> <p>iii. If the participant does not talk about top-down, government-led requirements that influence how they do their work, then rephrase: "What formal government requirements are in place that influence if and how you engage with those outside of your organisation?"</p> <p>iv. If the participant does not talk about their current or recent work experiences, critically within their own profession and organisation type, then rephrase: "Inside of your organisation, what rules limit or enhance the involvement of external groups?"</p> <p>v. If the participant does not talk about the unspoken, and more informal, rules and conventions that exist across their field of work, then rephrase: "Are there informal expectations in your field regarding how you should involve outside groups or individuals?"</p>	
2b	<p><i>If If the participant is negative in their response to Q2, ask:</i></p>	<p>Please do probe for elaborated responses and explanations, full of local, culturally-grounded, contextual influences. We are interested in the contextual influences that may be preventing the</p>	<p>RRING seeks to understand if there are patterns of rejection of public engagement with particular causes or motivations.</p>

	What are the main reasons for <u>not</u> involving outside individuals or organisations in the process of developing your work to date?	participant from acting, or in the conscious decisions that the participant has made not to act.	
Aligning with ethical values			
3	<p>Moving to ethics, what steps do you take to ensure that the <u>way you do your work</u> does not cause concerns for society?</p> <p><i>[NOTE: Depending on the answer, this question funnels participant questions down 3a) or 3b) paths below]</i></p>	<p>This question is phrased in an open way to avoid limiting the scope of participants’ responses by using somewhat loaded terms such as ‘ethical’ or ‘moral’. A key focus here is on the ethical/moral considerations of the participant doing their work, not merely just the ethics of the outcomes/outputs of their work. For example, it IS NOT simply about how the participant communicates their findings to society – indeed, that relates to the previous ‘public engagement’ questions – and it IS instead about how morally aligned the participant’s work is to the standards that society expects them to uphold.</p> <p>If the participant does not cover issues of ethics or morality, in terms of what is deemed acceptable by society for them to do their work, please clarify with: “Are there any particular protocols, practices, norms or standards you follow in your work to ensure that the work you do is ethically robust, i.e. is it considered as being fair and morally reasonable to everyone involved in the research?” Please take care to not focus too much on the individual interviewee. RRI is typically an aspect of how organisations and institutions function, how they are structured, and how they direct their activities internally and externally.</p>	<p>The aim of the project is to learn about the use of ethics and ethical standards in research and innovation. (Ethics = moral principles that govern a person's behaviour or work process)</p>
3a	<i>If the participant is positive in their response to Q3, ask:</i>	<i>For all 3a) questions, ONLY ask them if they have not already been covered in the open response to Q3).</i>	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. What affects how your work would cause concerns for groups or individuals outside your type of organisation? ii. How are <u>norms and practices</u> in your field affecting how you make sure your work would not cause concerns for by groups or individuals outside your type of organisation? iii. What government or <u>institutional policies and regulations</u> affect how you address ethics in your work? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. If the participant does not talk about the influences that are shaping the actions that they would have just talked about in responding to Q3, then rephrase: “Perhaps moral issues that certain groups in society indicate as being connected to your work?” ii. If the participant does not talk about the more informal, often unspoken conventions that drive what is deemed to be ‘normal’ (in an ethical sense) in them doing their work, then rephrase: “What informal expectations exist in your field about not causing concerns to outside groups or individuals?” iii. The final question is just to ensure that the implementation of ethical practices has been addressed. This question can be skipped if it was already addressed by previous responses. 	
3b	<p><i>If the participant is negative in their response to Q3, ask:</i></p> <p>Why do you not take actions to ensure your work would not cause concerns for outside groups or individuals?</p>		
Open access and open data			
4	<p>There is a lot of discussion about open and free access to <u>publication of research results</u> these days. How do you feel about this topic and its relevance to your work?</p> <p>And how do you feel about the idea of making <u>primary research data</u> you</p>	<p>Probe for the rationale and values underpinning these views if the participant’s response has not covered reasons behind their thoughts/beliefs on open access (i.e. we also want insights on their thinking behind their stated position). Specifically, ask: “Could you tell me more about why you feel that way?”</p>	<p>The aim is for the project to gain insights into practices for open access and open data, i.e. how the evidence beyond one’s research/innovation is shared with others.</p>

	<p>produce publicly available on an open basis?</p> <p><i>[NOTE: Depending on the answer, this question funnels participant questions down 4a) or 4b) paths below]</i></p>	<p>If the participant is not directly involved in producing primary research data, ask for their view about the general principle in their context (i.e. whether others should be expected to publish their data).</p>	
4a	<p><i>If the participant is positive in their response to Q4, ask:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. What <u>government</u> policies and regulations, affect whether you provide open access to outputs from your work? ii. What <u>institutional</u> policies and regulations affect whether you provide open access to outputs from your work? iii. What <u>norms or standard practices</u> in your field affect whether you provide open access to outputs from your work? 	<p><i>For all 4a) questions, ONLY ask them if they have not already been covered in the open response to Q4).</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. If the participant does not talk about top-down, government-led requirements that influence how they do their work, then rephrase: “What formal government requirements are in place that influence if and how you provide data on your work to the public?” ii. If the participant does not talk about the formal arrangements within their own organisation here, then rephrase: “What formal requirements or rules exist within your organisation that govern if and how your provide data on your work to the public?” iii. If the participant does not talk about the unspoken, and more informal, rules and conventions that exist across their field of work, then rephrase: “Are there any informal or unspoken conventions within your profession that lead you to provide data publicly?” 	
4b	<p><i>If the participant is negative in their response to Q4, ask:</i></p>		

	What are the main reasons for <u>not</u> sharing data and results openly and for no cost?		
Meeting societal needs			
5	<p>In what ways, if at all, does your work address societal needs?</p> <p><i>[NOTE: Depending on the answer, this question funnels participant questions down 5a) or 5b) paths below]</i></p>	If the participant does not talk about the societal needs themselves, and instead only discusses e.g. the connections between ‘needs’ and their work in finding ‘solutions’, then please ask: “With reference to examples, what societal needs are you responding to?”	<p>The priority for this question is to gather data on how different societies/cultures ‘construct’ problems in different ways (as part of accounting for particular ‘needs’ that they have identified). Indeed, what is a priority for one is by no means a priority for another.</p> <p>It is also useful to hear about how their work relates to global challenges in the specific contexts of the (Sustainable Development Goals-inspired) ‘domains’ on energy, waste management, bio-economy and ICT/digital.</p>
5a	<p><i>If the participant is positive in their response to Q5, ask:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. What <u>roles</u> do people/organizations outside of your institution have (if any) in assisting you to meet societal needs? ii. What <u>governmental policies and regulations, institutional policies or norms</u> in your field affect whether you are meeting societal needs? 	<p><i>For all 5a) questions, ONLY ask them if they have not already been covered in the open response to Q5).</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. If the participant does not talk about matters beyond their own organisation, then rephrase: “In what ways do you collaborate with colleagues beyond your organisation, in meeting the needs of society?” ii. A purpose of this question is to open up the line of questioning and ensure that any other <u>influences</u> are collected, and thus any/all insights are welcome. However, if 	

		the participant does continue talking about how practically they do ‘impactful’ work, then rephrase: “Are there any other influences that you feel affect if and how your work can meet the needs of society?”	
5b	<i>If the participant is negative in their response to Q5, ask:</i> Why is it <u>not</u> important for you address societal needs in your work?		
Anticipation			
6	As you develop your work plans, how do you take into account the future implications of your work? <i>[NOTE: Depending on the answer, this question funnels participant questions down 6a) or 6b) paths below]</i>	If the participant does not cover <u>future</u> implications, ask: “Please give us examples of some key future implications of your work.” AND, also ask: “And how do you consider these implication when planning your own work?”	Aim is to probe the degree to which the participant considers different future scenarios and how their own work (and indeed their own position as individual researchers/innovators) feeds in and out of those possible futures.
6a	<i>If the participant is positive in their response to Q6, ask:</i> i. How, if at all, do you address <u>perceptions</u> from outside individuals or organisations about the future implications of your work? ii. What <u>policies, regulations or norms</u> affect how you consider the future implications of your work?	<i>For all 6a) questions, ONLY ask them if they have not already been covered in the open response to Q6).</i> i. If the participant does not talk about the ways in which he/she thinks others (beyond their organisation) regard or understand how their work could impact the future in some way, then rephrase: “How do others perceive the future implications of your work, and how do you account for this?” ii. A purpose of this question is to open up the line of questioning and ensure that any other	

		rules-based <u>influences</u> are collected, and thus broad responses are welcome. However, if the participant does continue to describe future implications, without e.g. more deeply reflecting on the reasons that could be shaping those implications, then rephrase: “Are there formal or informal rules at any level that promote or hinder how your work prepares for the future?”	
6b	<p><i>If the participant is negative in their response to Q6, ask:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. What do you see as ‘<u>future implications</u>’ of your work? ii. Why are these future implications not important for you to consider? 		
Diversity and Gender Equality			
7	<p>There is a lot of discussion about increasing diversity and gender equality throughout the process of research and innovation. Diversity can be understood as promoting in research and innovation people who are otherwise underrepresented (women, ethnicities, or economic minorities, etc.). How do you feel about this topic’s relevance to your work?</p> <p><i>[NOTE: Depending on the answer, this question funnels participant questions down 7a) or 7b) paths below]</i></p>	<p>If the respondent does not say anything about gender issues, please ask a clarifying question: “How would you describe the working relationship between men and women (or men and other gender identities) in your field?”</p>	<p>Aim is to get insights on the role of diversity in research and innovation. Central to this are issues of inclusiveness, i.e. who are included/excluded from the research/innovation process, intentionally or not?</p>

7a	<p><i>Follow-up questions if participant gives a positive response about relevance of diversity in Q7:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. What <u>government</u> policies and regulations affect promoting diversity and gender equality in your field? ii. What <u>institutional</u> policies and regulations affect promoting diversity and gender equality in your field? iii. What <u>norms or standard practices</u> affect promoting diversity and gender equality in your field? 	<p><i>For all 7a) questions, ONLY ask them if they have not already been covered in the open response to Q7).</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. If the participant does not talk about top-down, government-led requirements that influence how they do their work, then rephrase: “How are government requirements, if at all, leading you to address diversity issues in your work?” ii. If the participant does not talk about the formal arrangements within their own organisation here, then rephrase: “Inside your organisation, what rules govern the inclusion of typically underrepresented individuals?” iii. If the participant does not talk about the unspoken, and more informal, rules and conventions that exist across their field of work, then rephrase: “Are there any informal or unspoken conventions within your profession that lead you to address diversity issues?” 	
7b	<p><i>If the participant gives a negative response about relevance of diversity in Q7, ask:</i></p> <p>What are the main reasons that promoting diversity in your field is not a relevant issue for your work?</p>		
Bringing it all together: responsibility			
8	<p>From your perspective, what does it mean to be ‘<u>responsible</u>’ in how you go about doing your work?</p>	<p>If the participant talks in too general terms and does not directly address what they think ‘responsibility’ is, then rephrase: “Is there anything that comes to mind</p>	<p>Aim to gain local understanding of the word and its possible relation to research and innovation.</p>

		<p>when you think about the word ‘responsible’ in relation to your work?”</p> <p>If the participant struggles to draw on examples to illustrate their thinking, please ask: “Moving away from your own work, to the work done by other professionals in your field: what other examples can you think of really ‘responsible’ research/innovation?” (Remember to choose the most appropriate “research” or “innovation” term here).</p>	<p>Although the project is on responsible research and innovation, we do not want to bias proceedings by mentioning ‘responsibility’ any earlier in the interview.</p>
9	<p>Before we finish, is there anything else you would like to add relating to what we have discussed?</p>	<p>This is a moment for the interview participant to raise anything that is important to them, or that may have come to mind in light of the full scope of questions that have now been revealed.</p> <p>Do not ask any follow-up questions that you are interested in knowing from the past questions. This is a moment for the participant to direct the conversation.</p>	<p>Given that this is a structured interview, we need to allow the participant space at the end to bring forward anything that the participant thinks is relevant to the questions that have been asked and/or that we may have missed in our questions.</p>

17 ANNEX 6: First page of a transcript (example)

Name of the interviewer	Jane Smith
Partner/Sub-contractor name doing the interview	ARU
Date of interview	25 February 2019
Duration of interview audio recording	50mins 14secs
Respondent	
- Code¹⁰	GB04
- Name	Jo-Ann Ruskin
- Company/Institute	University of Somewhere
- Gender	Female
- Key Domain(s)	Energy; waste management
- Stakeholder type	Civil society organisation
- Country	UK

Interviewer (JS): Hello and thank you for agreeing to give us this interview...

Participant (GM04): Thank you for the opportunity...

JS:

GM04:

¹⁰ Please use the International Vehicle Registration Code system to identify the relevant code for each country/interview: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/International_vehicle_registration_code

18 ANNEX 7: Post-interview email template, with transcript

Dear **[insert name]**,

Many thanks once again for so kindly giving up your time for an interview with me on **[insert date]**. It was a pleasure to learn more about your recent work and more generally to gather insights from you that will undoubtedly be of great use to our project.

I am emailing today to provide you with a copy of the interview transcript, which you can find attached. Should you wish to, you are able to look through the attached and let me know if there are any aspects that you would like removed – but, should I not hear back from you by **[insert date that is 1-week away from this email's send date]**, then I will assume you are happy with the transcript's contents. We will then move onto more deeply analysing and reflecting on what you told us, in the context of the wider pool of interviews.

Should you have any queries or feedback, then please do not hesitate to contact me.

Finally, I would like to invite you to take this brief survey on your experience being interviewed. This will be used to improve research practices by the RRING project internally. As a small thank you for participating in this survey, you will automatically be entered into a prize draw for a €50 shopping voucher.

You can access the survey by clicking here:

<https://angliaruskin.onlinesurveys.ac.uk/rring-t33-post-interview-survey>

Best wishes,

[interviewer name]

20 ANNEX 8: Checklists for planning: before and after interviews

BEFORE THE INTERVIEW

- Translation of docs into the local language:
 - Interview questions
 - Contact interview template
 - Project information sheet and consent form
- Ensure project information sheet and consent form have been sent to the interview participant
- Ensure you have had received consent before the interview starts, either via email before, or you should be ready to gain consent at the very start of the interview (before proceeding any further).
- Ensure you have covered all the domains, and also collected evidence (e.g. screenshot from organisation website) to demonstrate domain relevance/classification.
- Ensure you have covered the stakeholder types, and also collected evidence (e.g. screenshot from organisation website) to demonstrate stakeholder type relevance/classification.

AFTER THE INTERVIEW

- Whilst it is fresh in your mind (immediately after the interview), write some notes in response to the field note questions (see Annex 4).
- Complete field notes online questionnaire, within one week after the interview.
<https://angliaruskin.onlinesurveys.ac.uk/rring-field-notes>
- Transcribe and translate (when necessary), in accordance with transcript guidance and Annex 6.
- Produce a third version of each transcript that is anonymised.
- Submit the following to ARU via MS Teams (see sub-section 11.1 for guidance on where within MS Teams) for every interview conducted within 2 weeks of the interview taking place and/or by the final deadline as communicated by the task leader:
 - signed consent form
 - transcripts x3:
 - transcript in original language
 - transcript translated into English (non-anonymized, full version)
 - transcript translated into English (anonymized, to protect identity of interview participant)
 - audio recording
 - copy of email sent to interview participant, with a copy of the local language transcript and weblink to optional follow-up survey on their interview experience
 - Screenshots with information on respondents' background demonstrating their suitability for being interviewed
- Submit the following to ARU via MS Teams (see sub-section 11 for guidance on where within MS Teams), once all the interviews have been completed, by the final deadline as communicated by the task leader:
 - list of interview participants willing to participate in WP5 interviews

- statement of how you followed the interview participant selection criteria – with clear justifications provided for why deviations were unavoidable. For example, if not all domains and stakeholder types were covered, or if 40% female or other gender identities representation was not reached, the explanations are required.
- Send follow-up email to your interview participant, thanking them for their time and also confirming their transcript output.

21 ANNEX 9: Allocated number of interviews

Partner/subcontractor	Country	Number of interviews
UNESCO	Uruguay	5
Meiji	Singapore, Japan	15
NRF	Botswana, South Africa	18
DMU	Malawi, Italy	14
HSRW	Guatemala and Brazil	5
ARU	UK	8
CNR	Italy	3
CEDLa	Brazil	7
University of San Carlos	Guatemala	10
CPN	Serbia	7
PRIA	India	10
Yangon University of Education	Myanmar	10
Bintel Analytics	Malawi	10
Israel Institute of Technology	Israel	5
Russian-Tajik (Slavonic) University	Tajikistan	08
The Academy of Scientific Research and Technology (ASRT)	Egypt	10
R&D Maroc	Morocco	10
Royal Scientific Society	Jordan	8
Centro de Estudios y Proyectos (CEP S.R.L.)	Bolivia	10
AAAS	US	10
Total		183

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